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Factors Affecting Students Performance in Major Examinations Via LMS

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Abstract

This study presented the factors affecting students' performance in major examinations via LMS in Lipa City Colleges. A mixed method of research was utilized to serve the purpose of the study. It involves presenting, analyzing, and interpreting the existing factors that affects the performance of the students in major examinations using LMS in attempt to find out the relationship of their grade point average to the said factors. The researchers established an action plan that can alleviate the concerns on their experience in taking examinations in LMS. Lastly, the researchers proposed several activities for each factor to address the concerns that surfaced in the study. Orientation for major examination, keywording techniques, special examination, revitalization of LMS usage, and time allotment adjustment were the suggested actions for the mentioned concerns in this study.

Keywords: *major examination, students' performance, LMS*

Introduction

Today's newest and most well-known kind of distance education is online learning. It has significantly impacted post-secondary education over the last decade, and the trend will continue. Online learning is a form of education delivered via the internet, also known as e-learning, among other things. On the other hand, it is one sort of distance learning which refers to any learning that takes place at a distance rather than in a traditional classroom.

Online learning includes a variety of technologies such as the internet, email, chat, new groups and texts, and audio and video conferencing supplied across computer networks. It allows the learner to progress at their own pace and their convenience. Online education necessitates a significant investment of time and money and proper planning. Learners use e-learning technologies that are freely available to everyone. Through its innovative and dynamic content delivery, e-learning has restored the joy of studying and has proven to be more engaging to students.

E-learning is a formal learning system that makes use of electronic resources. While education can take place within (or outside) the classroom, e-learning relies heavily on computer technology and the internet. When the COVID-19 virus surfaced, traditional educational techniques were supplanted with e-learning because social gatherings in educational institutions are potential avenues for the virus to spread despite the problems and analyzed numbers that indicate that students are less likely to profit from this sort of education. E-learning is the best choice available to ensure that disease do not spread.

The learning management system (LMS) is a software program or web-based technology used to design, implement, and evaluate a learning process. It is used in eLearning and, in its most basic form, consists of two elements: a server that conducts the main operation and a user interface that instructors, students, and administrators control. LMS has many application varieties depending on the software developer that makes it. To name a few, Google Class, Canvass, and LMS are some of the most well-known software out in the market.

These kinds of instructional technology can contribute significantly to the optimal way of adjusting educational approaches to boost students' academic achievement. Exploring the potential of these learning tools can provide more guidance for how blended learning should be used more successfully in language lessons, promoting diversity in students' learning experiences. It will also provide language educators with relevant interventions for integrating the indicated application into language-blended learning to maximize student engagement.

In January 2020, in the onslaught of COVID-19, Lipa City Colleges decided to transition from traditional classes to e-learning to continue teaching students despite the lack of physical contact. This event is the first time the institution has used online platform modalities and pedagogies to send lessons to its students. Initially, the instructors and professors used Facebook and Messenger to teach and relay information to their students. Shortly after that, they incorporated using LMS but started using google classroom as it suffices the urgency of the sudden educational transition. It is free to use and easily accessible.

In the following semester, Lipa City Colleges stopped using Google Classroom and decided to use another LMS platform. In August 2020, the institution bought a license to use LMS as its learner management system. LMS is what the whole institution started using, which is the same platform they used until today. This software serves as the school's permanent LMS that has already been up and running for five semesters.

However, the difficulties of online learning can have a significant influence on youngsters; motivation, self-discipline, and the desire to study are only a few of the issues they confront. The inefficiency of technology, the difficulty for students to understand the information taught, and online learning induces social isolation, and a lack of communication skills are all adverse effects. Individual learning styles, learning environments, and parental engagement are all factors that influence how well a student's education performs

in online learning.

Assessment is one of the essential educational tools accessible for various purposes, including maximizing learning and motivating students to improve their performance to fulfill pre-determined goals and standards. It has assisted teachers in assessing students' progress over time by providing unannounced quizzes, periodic assessments, and final examinations internally. As a result, assessments are frequently seen and used as measures of school progress and success rather than as tools to study the causes of learning success or failure.

Major examination in academic institutions is a form of assessment that the learners gain their knowledge and skills. The considerable analysis assesses if a student has gained information and skills. In a newly implemented way of learning, major examination becomes more efficient in determining whether a student learns. Major examination becomes the analysis of the grades of students. It can also acquire information for specific students who require interventions or remedial work for a subject using significant tests. It would also be good to review whether they effectively communicated the lessons to their students as future educators. In that way, they can improve their teaching and student interactions. It has a most significant part in students' final grades because the major examinations combine all the lessons starting the first quarter to the last quarter; it is a random questionnaire to determine if students can recall lessons from the start. It evaluates if students take time to read and comprehend the lessons rather than trust the stock knowledge.

In Lipa City Colleges, four major examinations correspond to four grading terms. Major examinations in LCC weigh 40% of the total grade point average in general and professional education courses. Examinations have a significant function in the educational system as a whole and the process of learning. Tests are excellent tools for gauging how much pupils have learned about a course. It is another method for determining strengths and shortcomings. This study will demonstrate the effects of using LMS during major examinations and how it varies over the terms since major assessments make up a large portion of the student's academic performance.

These observations and information inspired the researchers to pursue this study to determine if the future educators' performance was affected during this online learning- specifically on their experiences in taking major examinations using LMS. As education students, the researchers are aware and have experienced many problems during this online learning. The researchers and other people need to understand the students' situation that affects their academic performance. Knowing about online learning and different online platforms in connection to the factors that affect it will help achieve a more favorable and desirable performance and implementation.

Research Questions

This research aimed to identify the factor affecting students' performance in major examinations via LMS as a basis for future enhancement programs. With this, they said research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the grade point average of the education students in general and professional education subjects during online classes?
2. What are the factors affecting the performance of the education students in General Education and Professional Education Subjects during major examinations via LMS in terms of:
 - 2.1 personal condition;
 - 2.2 study habits;
 - 2.3 home related aspect;
 - 2.4 school related aspect; and
 - 2.5 teacher related aspect?
3. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 3.1 GPA during online classes; and
 - 3.2 factors affecting students' performance?

Literature Review

In the twenty-first century, the advancement of digital technology has significantly altered our educational system. In higher, education the use of the internet in teaching and learning has become more frequent (Bhagat et al., 2016). The fact is that students now have access to a new mode of instructional delivery called online learning.

Globally, online learning is becoming increasingly popular. Online learning presents demographic problems as well as differences in student preparation. Blended learning at a higher level of education in online learning is commonly used (Dziuban et al., 2018). The acceptance of student learning during the learning process is a component that determines online learning success. Two elements influencing online learning recognition are service quality and confidence (Lee et al., 2009). Service quality constructs include instructor traits, instructional materials, and learning design content, and the belief construct includes perceived effectiveness and perceived ease of use.

According to Tu and Mclsaac (2004), this situation demonstrates that people participate in online commerce knowingly and actively by paying attention to the social environment, online communication, and interactivity. Furthermore, instructors must consider the value of social presence (Wise et al., 2004), the ease of speaking and participating in an online setting (Cobb, 2009), time duration, and gender while implementing online learning. (Tasir & Al- Dheleai, 2019)

In students' eyes, online learning should focus on course design, learner motivation, time management, and online technology convenience. According to Moorhouse (2020), synchronous and asynchronous online learning creates courses during a pandemic. The teacher uses an asynchronous teaching style with PowerPoint material and voice notes. Video conferencing software is used to provide synchronous instruction (VCS). Individual assignments, group discussions, preliminary explanations linked to the topic, and structured exercises are all things that can help boost knowledge of online learning.

The preparation of the material module had a direct impact on the teaching personnel. Implementing online learning that is both quick and unprepared has an impact on the teaching staff's perceptions of knowledge transfer Sohel and Power (2010). Teachers in China grasp online when the pandemic COVID-19, among other things, the incapacity to teach online, pupils and teachers confront difficulties with online learning and the ambiguous modalities of training that match (Zhang et al., 2020).

However, there are numerous disadvantages to e-learning, the most significant of which is obtaining knowledge solely on a theoretical foundation and putting what learners have learned into practice without applying practical skills. Many learners and instructors may be interested in a face-to-face learning experience. Other issues arise from online examinations, which may be restricted to objective questions. In addition to other difficulties that are constantly associated with the misuse of technology, issues connected to the security of online learning programs and user reliability are among the obstacles of e-learning (Gautam, 2020; Mukhtar et al., 2020).

The most significant disadvantage of using e-learning is the need for more critical personal connections between students and teachers and among peers (Somayeh et al., 2016). Compared to wealthy countries, developing countries confront numerous problems when implementing e-learning, including poor internet connectivity, a lack of expertise in using information and communication technology, and poor content production (Aung & Khaing, 2015).

Learning Management System

LMS plays a significant role in enhancing and facilitating teaching and learning in today's accessible digital environment. LMS allows teachers to focus on building meaningful pedagogical activities while delivering instructions and electronic resources to promote and supplement student learning in a collaborative environment (Kattoua et al., 2016). Yakubu (2019) asserted that a learning management system (LMS) is a web-based system with many pedagogical and course administration functions. Through these educational technologies, LMS can facilitate group conversations, debates, document sharing, assignment submissions, quizzes, grading, and course evaluations (Bove, & Conklin, 2020).

In addition, (Bergen, French, & Hawkins, 2015), an LMS can allow students to assess, reflect, and monitor their learning while also allowing teachers, parents, and supervisors to monitor the continuous learning process. The current LMS applications and features provide insight into the instructor and student activities, allowing supervisors and parents to monitor them, report deficiencies, and make quick decisions. Furthermore, Bervell and Umar (2017a, b) mentioned that LMS could increase access, lower costs, and improve the quality of education, allowing SSA institutions to accommodate the expanding student population (Andersson & Grönlund, 2009; Unwin et al., 2010).

Emelyanova and Voronina (2014) also conducted a study at Russian National Research University to establish not only the participants' purpose, readiness, and efficacies in using LMS but also their evaluations of its efficacy, usability, and convenience of use. The findings found that, while the teacher and students had no issues with the computer and LMS use, the students did not view LMSs as beneficial learning tools, LMSs, according to the teacher and the students, serve as storage for course content. Furthermore, students did not believe LMSs were beneficial for online work and communication activities, preferring face-to-face learning.

Moreover, Alkhasawneh and Alqahtani (2019) emphasized the importance of expanding the use of asynchronous tools in a learning management system. According to Alkhasawneh and Alqahtani (2019), asynchronous learning provides flexibility because learners can reflect and complete tasks. Learning outcomes vary among students utilizing an LMS, with low-achieving students often needing help submitting assignments by the due date. In contrast, high-achieving students sometimes find it challenging to surpass the deadline (Watson & Watson, 2012).

Najmul Islam (2016) advises students to take advantage of LMS capabilities to improve collaboration during class discussions, which would help boost students' intrinsic motivation and learning. Utilizing learner profiles in an LMS gives instructors a methodical approach to fostering learner competencies (Kimmons et al., 2019). Incorporating LMS into various activities encourages student learning and self-control (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020). Utilizing an LMS gives practitioners flexibility, customization, and adaptability (Kehrwald & Parker, 2019). Innovative online teachers are encouraging the use of LMS to support user-driven online learning environments that use a range of media and communication technologies and encourage learner choice in the selection and usage of online learning tools (Kehrwald & Parker, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

The study was conducted to assess the factors affecting students' performance in Lipa City Colleges College of Education in their major examinations via LMS. The researchers used the mixed-method (quantitative and qualitative) type of research in this study.

Participants

The participants of this study were the twenty-five 4th year education students of Lipa City Colleges College of Education. Several factors were also considered for the students to become eligible study respondents. In the conduct of the study, the students should at least experience taking online classes and examinations via LMS from the institution. This condition is to ensure that there are no external factors that can alter the grades of the students written on their respective prospectuses.

Second, the students must have taken the same General Education and Professional Education courses within the same batch based on the academic year for the data collection to become uniform and homogenous. This condition is to maintain consistency and accuracy in the study's outcome. Judging from the considerations mentioned earlier, they were the first batch in the College of Education to experience taking major examinations through LMS and are, therefore, the most appropriate participants in the initial conduct of this study.

Instruments

Complete enumeration was used in the study due to the small population of eligible respondents. The census or complete enumeration method is used to get all members' responses in a specific population (Oulte, 2011). The researchers collected and obtained a copy of the students' prospectus to determine their performance. Questionnaire was used in gathering data about the factors affecting students' performance in major examinations using LMS along with personal conditions, study habits, home-related aspects, school-related aspects, and teacher-related aspects. The survey questionnaire used the Likert Scale as the basis for ascertaining which of the reasons impacts the specific factors the most and the least.

A Likert Scale is widely used in survey research to assess opinions, attitudes, or behaviors. This rating scale easily operationalizes personality traits or perceptions (Bhandari, 2022). Along with the survey questionnaire, a guided interview was also done to get the personal verbal answers of the respondents. The interview questions were also anchored on the factors mentioned above. The said research instrument was considered valid and reliable based on the researchers' readings of several theses materials. The said research instrument was also checked, validated, and approved by the research adviser and was further validated and reviewed by the board of panelists.

Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents using modern channels to maximize the efficiency of the data gathering. Social media platforms were used to reach this study's respondents, specifically Facebook Messenger. The message contained a short explanation of why the researchers conducted the study. Together with the message was the soft copy of the questionnaire that the respondents were encouraged to fill up. The respondents were expected to fill up the online survey as truthfully as they could for the overall reliability of the study.

This data-gathering method was the best option for acquiring accurate data while maintaining little to no physical contact. This method ensured that this study did not contribute to any highly contagious COVID-19 virus transmission by following the quarantine protocols ordered by the government. The researchers also provided physical copies of the survey for those respondents who wished to participate face-to-face in the study while still following the health protocols and guidelines.

The respondents were asked to answer the survey by determining which reason under each factor impacted them the most-1 having no impact to 5 having a very high impact. The predetermined reasons under each factor were meticulously chosen according to the related articles found within this study. The guided interview was also done on various platforms depending on the availability of the respondents. The interviews were done vis-a-vis or through CAPI (Computer-Assisted Personal Interview).

Ethical Considerations

In this study, ethical considerations were considered in the data-gathering procedure.

The study's respondents were not required to fill out their full names on the online survey. This consideration is to give them a choice to keep their anonymity in the data collection. It was still ensured that the respondent was eligible because the researchers asked for their prospectuses since it was also used in the data interpretation. They, however, had a choice to stay anonymous on the survey questionnaire part. To the respondents who fully disclosed their names in the entirety of the survey, rest assured that the researchers did not leak any information regarding the respondents concerning the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Given the situation where the respondents were not willing to answer the questionnaire, the researchers did their best to explain the purposes of why such a study was conducted. This exemplification was to convince the respondents to participate in the data gathering of the study. Nevertheless, the researchers still did not force them to participate or coerce them to join the said data gathering if they did not want to participate. They were also given the freedom to withdraw in the middle of the data gathering if they felt the need to do so.

Results

This section shows the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the respondents.

Table 1. *Grade Point Average of the Education Students During Online Classes*

Grade	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1.49 - 1.25	1	4.00	4
1.74 - 1.50	14	56.00	1
1.99 - 1.75	6	24.00	2
2.24 - 2.00	4	16.00	3
Total	25	100	
Performed Best		1.42	
Performed Least		2.17	
Mean Grade		1.75	

As presented in the table, the GPA of 1.74 - 1.50 got the highest frequency count of 14 or 56% at rank 1, whereas 1.49 - 1.25 obtained the least frequency count of one or 4 % at rank 4. The highest grade was 1.42, the lowest was 2.17, and the mean grade was 1.75.

Table 2. *Factors Affecting the Performance of the Education Students in General Education and Professional Education Subjects During Major Examinations via LMS in Terms of Personal Condition*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>In terms of personal conditions, I...</i>			
Am always prepared for the upcoming major examinations.	3.84	High Impact	2
Feel motivated to answer major examinations using LMS	3.52	High Impact	8
Can maintain focus during online examinations	3.60	High Impact	5.5
Maintain a good sleeping schedule so I can answer my online examinations.	3.56	High Impact	7
Get ample sleep when there is an online examination the next day.	3.60	High Impact	5.5
Am not bothered by the time pressure during online examinations.	3.76	High Impact	3.5
Have a work plan in studying for my upcoming major examinations.	3.76	High Impact	3.5
Manage my time during online classes.	3.96	High Impact	1
Composite Mean	3.58	High Impact	

As given in the table, the respondents assessed that managing their time during online classes has a high impact during online examination via LMS, with the highest weighted mean of 3.96 and the highest rank of 1.

Table 3. *Factors Affecting the Performance of the Education Students in General Education and Professional Education Subjects During Major Examination via LMS in Terms of Study Habits*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>In terms of study habits, I...</i>			
Find a place to study before my online examinations.	4.28	Very High Impact	1.5
Rely on my soft copies to review before my online examinations.	3.76	High Impact	6
Can study well even without a printed copy of the lesson.	3.16	Moderate Impact	8
Use my gadget to study before using it for leisure.	3.80	High Impact	4.5
Have a scheduled time in studying for my major examinations.	4.00	High Impact	3
Can manage my time when I am studying at home.	3.80	High Impact	4.5
Like studying with my friends or in a group.	3.72	High Impact	7
Can review the lessons by myself.	4.28	Very High Impact	1.5
Composite Mean	3.85	High Impact	

As gleaned in the table, the respondents answered that finding a place to study before online examinations and reviewing the lessons by themselves have a very high impact during online examinations via LMS, which got the highest and equal-weighted means of 4.28 and the highest ranks of 1.5.

Table 4. *Factors Affecting the Performance of the Education Students in General Education and Professional Education Subjects During Major Examination via LMS in Terms of Home-Related Aspects*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>In terms of home-related aspects, I...</i>			
Have a designated area where I study and take online examinations.	4.40	Very High Impact	1
Can look for a place in my house to take examinations easily in case I don't have a designated area.	3.76	High Impact	3
Have a room free from noise and external nuisances.	3.48	High Impact	4.5
Have a personal room at home.	4.08	High Impact	2
Have a stable internet connection at home.	3.48	High Impact	4.5
Use mobile data when I take online examinations.	3.08	Moderate Impact	7

Have an area that has minimal schedules of power interruptions.	3.04	Moderate High Impact	8
Have a household that is quiet and almost noise-free.	3.36	Moderate Impact	6
Composite Mean	3.59	High Impact	

As written in the table, the respondents affirmed that having a designated area where they study and take online examinations has a very high impact during online examinations via LMS, which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.40 and the highest rank of 1.

Table 5. *Factors Affecting the Performance of the Education Students in General Education and Professional Education Subjects During Major Examination via LMS in Terms of School-Related Aspects*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>In terms of school-related aspects, I...</i>			
Can access my school portal easily.	4.12	High Impact	2
Have a LMS account that is stable and glitch-free.	4.08	High Impact	3.5
can easily navigate LMS.	4.00	High Impact	5.5
Have a user-friendly LMS.	4.00	High Impact	5.5
Prefer answering exams using LMS.	3.60	High Impact	8
Receive organized schedule for online examinations.	3.96	High Impact	7
Receive announcements for major examinations from the school with ample preparation time.	4.08	High Impact	3.5
Get announcements from the school for the schedule of online examinations.	4.20	Very High Impact	1
Composite Mean	4.01	High Impact	

As revealed in the table, the respondents acknowledged that getting announcements from the school for the schedule of online examinations has a very high impact during online examinations via LMS, which obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.20 and the highest rank of 1.

Table 6. *Factors Affecting the Performance of the Education Students in General Education and Professional Education Subjects During Major Examination via LMS in Terms of Teacher-Related Aspects*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>In terms of teacher-related aspects, the teacher...</i>			
Is very energetic and dynamic during online examinations.	3.84	High Impact	8
gives pointers to review during online examinations.	4.08	High Impact	2
Shares the details on what to expect during online examinations.	4.00	High Impact	3.5
Is approachable in LMS.	3.92	High Impact	6.5
Is reachable in LMS during online exams.	3.92	High Impact	6.5
Is lenient in LMS during online examinations.	4.00	High Impact	3.5
Is equipped in utilizing LMS.	4.20	Very High Impact	1
Always uses LMS.	3.96	High Impact	5
Composite Mean	3.99	High Impact	

As reflected in the table, the respondents acknowledged that their teacher’s ability to utilize LMS has a very high impact. It obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.20 and the highest rank of 1.

Table 7. *Relationship Between Grade Point Average During Online Classes and Factors Affecting Students’ Performance*

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
<i>Grade Point Average Versus Factors Affecting Student Performance</i>				
Personal Condition	0.35	0.04316	p<0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Study Habits	0.34	0.04816	p<0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Home-Related Aspect	0.07	0.36976	p>0.05, Accept Ho	Not Significant
School-Related Aspect	0.04	0.42472	p>0.05, Accept Ho	Not Significant
Teacher-Related Aspect	0.05	0.40619	p>0.05, Accept Ho	Not Significant

As stated in the table, when the grade point average of the respondents was compared to their assessment of the factors affecting students’ performance during major examinations of the factors affecting students’ performance during major examinations via LMS, the computed r-values of 0.35 for personal conditions and 0.34 for study habits have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the computed r-values of 0.07 for home-related aspects, 0.04 for school-related aspects, and 0.05, thus accepting also the null hypothesis.

Discussion

According to the data, the grade point average of education students during online classes has a high impact on the student's

performance during online classes; it states that students learn more effectively in online classes with a well-structured and appealing e-learning course design that includes visual information.

Moreover, motivation improves the quality of learning students get by using the LMS. The respondents answered that personal condition has a high impact on the performance of education students in general education and professional education subjects during major examinations via LMS.

Moreover, the respondents assessed that study habit has a high impact on the performance of the education students in general education and professional education subjects during major examinations via LMS.

On the other hand, respondents assessed that the home-related aspect significantly affects the student's performance in general education and professional education subjects during major examinations via LMS.

The respondents assessed that school-related aspect has a high impact on the education students' performance in general education and professional education subjects during major examinations via LMS.

On the other hand, respondents assessed that teacher-related aspects greatly impacted the student's performance in general education and professional education subjects during major examinations via LMS.

Grade point average of the respondents has highly significant relationships to personal conditions and study habits; and no significant relationships to home, school, and teacher-related aspects.

Conclusion

Several conclusions can be drawn from this conducted study. (1) Most of the respondents' grade point average lies within the mean grade bracket of the students of the College of Education. (2) In terms of personal conditions, managing time during online classes has the highest impact among all items. On the other hand, the motivation to answer major examinations via LMS was found to have the most negligible impact. In conclusion, the students need more motivation to answer major examinations using LMS. This factor is significant to the performance of the students. Regarding study habits, finding a place to study before an online examination was deemed the most impactful. However, the researchers found that most education students can only study nicely with a printed copy of the lesson. Therefore, an action to obtain printed copies of the lesson is needed. This factor was found to be significant to the education students' performance in major examinations via LMS. In home-related aspects, having a designated area to study has the most impact on answering major examinations via LMS. Meanwhile, having an area with minimal power interruptions has the most negligible impact on this factor. This finding concludes that home-related aspects concerning the education students' performance in major examinations via LMS are affected mainly by power interruptions.

However, this factor is deemed not significant. In school-related aspects, the students highly appreciate when they get announcements from the school regarding the schedule of online examinations. However, they least prefer to answer examinations using LMS. This finding exemplifies that a plan to revitalize the usage of LMS is needed. Based on the data, this factor was also seen as insignificant but still requires action since the interview revealed that they lack knowledge in navigating LMS during major examinations. In teacher-related aspects, teachers are highly equipped to utilize LMS when giving out exams. However, the study also revealed that teachers could have been more energetic and dynamic during online examinations. Therefore, a plan for time allotment adjustment should be made. This factor was also found insignificant, but an action to align the examination items to the allotted period in LMS is still needed. It was seen as the problem as to why the teachers are said to not be dynamic, according to the respondents of this study. (3) It is concluded that the performance of Lipa City Colleges' education students in major examinations is significantly affected by personal conditions and study habits only. Home, school, and teacher-related aspects were not considered significant factors in their major examination performance. However, an action plan must still be made to address the concerns regarding the aforementioned factors-regardless of their significance. (4) To address the concerns that surfaced in this study, the researchers established a tabulated action plan to improve the experience and performance of the student in major examinations via LMS.

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